

A Novel Method for Suicidal Thought Detection

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Abstract—Suicide is a critical issue in modern society. Early detection and prevention of suicide attempts should be addressed to save people's life. Current suicidal thought detection methods include clinical methods based on the interaction between social workers or experts and the targeted individuals and machine learning techniques with feature engineering or deep learning for automatic detection based on online social contents. In this paper, we propose a methodology based on experimental research for building a suicidal ideation detection system using publicly available Reddit datasets, word-embedding approaches, such as TF-IDF and Word2Vec, for text representation, and hybrid deep learning and machine learning algorithms for classification.

Keywords—Suicidal thought detection, social media content, machine learning

I. INTRODUCTION

Mental health issues, such as anxiety and depression, are becoming increasingly concerned in modern society, as they turn out to be especially severe in developed countries and emerging markets. Severe mental disorders without effective treatment can turn to suicidal thoughts or even suicide attempts. Some online posts contain much negative information and generate problematic phenomena such as cyberstalking and cyberbullying. Consequences can be severe and risky since such lousy information is often engaged in some form of social cruelty, leading to rumors or even mental damage. Research shows that there is a link between cyberbullying and suicide [1].

Victims overexposed to too many negative messages or events may become depressed and desperate; even worse, some may commit suicide.

The reasons that people commit suicide are complicated. People with depression are highly likely to commit suicide, but many without depression can also have suicidal thoughts [2]. According to the American Foundation for Suicide Prevention (AFSP), suicide factors fall under three categories: health factors, environmental factors, and historical factors [3]. Ferrari et al. [4] found that mental health issues and substance use disorders are attributed to the factors of suicide. O'Connor and Nock [5] conducted a thorough review of the psychology of suicide and summarized psychological risks as personality and individual differences, cognitive factors, social factors, and negative life events.

Suicidal Ideation Detection (SID) determines whether the person has suicidal ideation or thoughts by given tabular data of a person or textual content written by a person. Due to the advances in social media and online anonymity, an increasing number of individuals turn to interact with others on the Internet. Online communication channels are becoming a new way for people to express their feelings, suffering, and suicidal tendencies. Hence, online channels have naturally started to act as a surveillance tool for suicidal ideation, and mining social content can improve suicide prevention [6]. Strange social phenomena are emerging, e.g., online communities reaching an agreement on self-mutilation and copycat suicide. For example, a social network phenomenon called the "Blue Whale Game"¹ in 2016 uses many tasks (such as self-

harming) and leads game members to commit suicide in the end. Suicide is a critical social issue and takes thousands of lives every year. Thus, it is necessary to detect suicidality and to prevent suicide before victims end their life. Early detection and treatment are regarded as the most effective ways to prevent potential suicide attempts. Potential victims with suicidal ideation may express their thoughts of committing suicide in fleeting thoughts, suicide plans, and role-playing. Suicidal ideation detection is to find out these risks of intentions or behaviors before tragedy strikes. A meta-analysis conducted by McHugh et al. [7] shown statistical limitations of ideation as a screening tool, but also pointed out that people’s expression of suicidal ideation represents their psychological distress. Effective detection of early signals of suicidal ideation can identify people with suicidal thoughts and open a communication portal to let social workers mitigate their mental issues. The reasons for suicide are complicated and attributed to a complex interaction of many factors [5], [8]. To detect suicidal ideation, many researchers conducted psychological and clinical studies [9] and classified responses of questionnaires [10]. Based on their social media data, artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning techniques can predict people’s likelihood of suicide [11], which can better understand people’s intentions and pave the way for early intervention. Detection on social content focuses on feature engineering [12], [13], sentiment analysis [14], [15], and deep learning [16], [17], [18]. Those methods generally require heuristics to select features or design artificial neural network architectures for learning rich representation. The research trend focuses on selecting more useful features from people’s health records and developing neural architectures to understand the language with suicidal ideation better

II. METHODS

This section presents the main components of the proposed suicidal thought detection system (STDS) framework using linguistics, signs, and activities on Suicide Watch, which is a sub-platform of the Reddit social media news aggregation platform. Fig.1 presents the steps of this framework. This is the most important stage of

our experimental work on online suicide thought detection.

Fig. 1: Steps of proposed work

A. Dataset:

We used a publicly available Reddit dataset downloaded from the Kaggle website. The dataset comprised 232,074 posts to SuicideWatch from 16 December 2008–2 January 2021, including 116,037 suicidal and 116,037 non-suicidal posts shown in Fig 2. The term “suicide watch” refers to a monitoring procedure intended to prevent suicide attempts. The term typically applies to individuals in jails, hospitals, mental facilities, and army bases. Individuals suspected of displaying suicide warning signals, meaning that they may be at risk of intentional self-harm, are placed under suicide watch.

Unnamed: 0	text	class
0	2 Ex Wife Threatening SuicideRecently I left my ...	suicide
1	3 Am I weird I don't get affected by compliments...	non-suicide
2	4 Finally 2020 is almost over... So I can never ...	non-suicide
3	8 i need helpjust help me im crying so hard	suicide
4	9 I'm so lostHello, my name is Adam (16) and I've...	suicide

Fig. 2: Dataset

B. Pre-Processing:

This step aims to filter textual posts to eliminate noise before applying feature extraction and embedding techniques, and to produce a word vector for classification. It includes stop word removal, punctuation removal, lowercasing, tokenization, and lemmatization. We employed the Natural Language Toolkit (NLTK) [18] and performed basic tasks to preprocess the dataset.

- Punctuation, emoji, and numerical digit removal: this process removes the characters “?, !, :, ;, ’,” and emoji to make the text easily processable.
- Stop word removal: this process removes words such as “the”, “a”, “an”, and “in”, which have no contribution to the operation of the model.
- Lowercasing: this process lowercases all words.
- Tokenization: this process splits each sentence into its basic parts, such as words, phrases, and other pieces of information.
- Lemmatization: this process combines inflected forms of words into their root form.
- To use a DL neural network technique to distinguish between suicidal and non-suicidal posts, all sequences of texts in the dataset must have equal real-value vectors. To accomplish this task, the post-padding sequence method was used.

C. Word Embedding:

Word embedding is a text representation process widely used for language modeling and feature representation in NLP. It converts each word and sentence of a given text into low-dimensional feature vectors to be analyzed by ML algorithms. In this work, we used TF-IDF and Word2Vec [19] to extract vector representations of words and sentences for suicidal/non-suicidal classification.

1) *TF-IDF:*

TF-IDF is a representation and feature extraction approach used in text categorization models [20] and is widely employed for understanding natural language and information retrieval. This statistical method is particularly used to measure the importance of a pattern in a text. Its first component, TF, identifies the occurrence of specific words to determine the similarity between them, as follows:

$$TF(w)_d = n_w(d) / |d| \tag{1}$$

Set D points to a set of documents, and d denotes a single document, $d \in D$. Each document is represented as a group of sentences and words w , and $n_w(d)$ is the number of recurrent words w in document d . Therefore, the size of document d is calculated as follows:

$$|d| = \sum_{w \in d} n_w(d) \tag{2}$$

The frequency at which a word appears in the document is expressed in Equation (2).

IDF, the second component of *TF-IDF*, is used to compute the number of documents in a textual corpus in which a specific word appears, as follows:

$$IDF(w)_d = 1 + \log(|D| / |\{d: D | w \in d\}|) \tag{3}$$

The *TF-IDF* for word w associated with document d and corpus D can be calculated as:

$$TF-IDF = TF(w)_d \times IDF(w)_D \tag{4}$$

Generally, *TF-IDF* uses a document-term matrix to generate different text classification systems.

2) *Word2Vec:*

Word2Vec is another method for obtaining word embeddings—that is, for extracting numeric representations of words—in a given text that is widely used in language modeling and feature learning. This algorithm, developed by Google, has

a two-layer neural network structure to extract vector representations and predict the context of a given word in a text. Although it has a limit to handling words that are not in the selected vocabulary size as maximum features, it is nevertheless optimal for NLP tasks [21] since it finds associations between words and sentences. In this work, Word2Vec was used to convert and map each word in the dataset used for training and testing into a 32-dimensional word representation vector.

D. Classification Model

After obtaining word embeddings for each post content using TF-IDF and Word2Vec, supervised ML algorithms—namely, hybrid CNN–bidirectional LSTM (BiLSTM) DL algorithm—were used for classification.

The CNN–BiLSTM model used in this study includes an embedding layer, a convolutional layer, a max pooling layer, bidirectional LSTM layers, and a softmax classification layer.

1) *Embedding Layer*: This is the first hidden neural network layer. Its structure is based on three parameters of the CNN–BiLSTM architecture: input sequence length, embedding dimension, and maximum features. The input sequence length is the average length of each post in the dataset, which was set to 430 words. Maximum features are the 30,000 most recurring words extracted from the training dataset using Word2Vec. The embedding dimension adopts the size vector of each word vectorized into sequences of integers, and it was specified as 32-dimensional word vectors. The main task of the embedding layer is to create an input embedding matrix for each word selected from the training.

2) *Convolutional Layer*: The input data for this layer are a word-embedding matrix that is merged by applying a convolutional operation to construct feature maps [22]. The convolutional layer performs computations on the input-embedding matrix for selected words provided by an embedding layer. It uses filters to pass across the matrix to collect sequence information and reduce the dimensions of the input sequence. It uses four main parameters—number of filters, kernel size, type of padding required, and nonlinear activation

function—to produce the feature map to the following layer.

3) *Max Pooling Layer*: In this layer, the feature map is passed using the convolutional kernel. It performs a pooling operation on the feature map matrix by calculating the maximum value from a pooling window and uses it to reduce the dimensionality of the downsampled feature map of an input sequence to enhance the model's classification performance.

4) *BiLSTM Layers*: LSTM, a type of RNN, is used in various artificial intelligence and DL tasks, including NLP, image processing, sequence mining, and text mining [23]. It is capable of learning long-term dependencies, which allows it to retain information for long periods. The memory cells employed in LSTM can ultimately transfer the results of prior data features to the output. However, feature learning occurs only in a forward direction, thus ignoring backward construction and reducing the performance of the ML system. To tackle this problem, BiLSTM has two hidden layers in opposite directions connected to a single output. Thus, the input training data are processed in both forward and backward directions. The structure of the hidden layers includes four gates, which determine the amount of past sequence information that should be ignored and the amount of context that should be carried forward. This makes BiLSTM ideal for identifying suicidal content in social media posts.

5) *Softmax Layer*: This is an output layer [24] that we used to estimate the probability of a post being suicidal or non-suicidal. To avoid vanishing problems, the softmax function uses a text feature vector acquired as a consequence of the LSTM layers and divides it into dataset classes.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

This section presents the empirical results obtained from the experiments conducted to detect suicidal ideation in social media posts using textual features. In the first experiment, based on the learning of word embeddings extracted from post content using tf-idf and word2vec, we used hybrid dl (cnn–bilstm) to create an sids that can be used to classify social media posts as suicidal or non-suicidal.

posts, the proposed system may help identify individuals who require medical treatment and reduce suicide rates.

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